

**Factors Influencing Tertiary Students' Use of ChatGPT in Their Education:
New Zealand Context**

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Abstract

Since ChatGPT offers free access for everyone, it has created a new phenomenon and has the potential to disrupt the education industry. The primary purpose of this quantitative study is to understand the factors that influence the use of ChatGPT in tertiary education, how it motivates students to learn and how the potential misuse negatively affects the use of ChatGPT in New Zealand. An empirical study was conducted with 340 tertiary students in Auckland, covering the New Zealand Qualifications Framework (NZQF) from level 4 to level 10, which revealed that one-third of students in this group did not adopt ChatGPT for various reasons. For the other two-thirds of students, while they highly recognised the risk of plagiarism, they were still willing to adopt ChatGPT for their studies. By understanding from the students' perspective in using ChatGPT in their studies, it provided the implications and recommendations for all the educational stakeholders and AI companies for their considerations to improve their respective areas.

Keywords: ChatGPT, Higher Education Institutes (HEI), Tertiary Education, New Zealand

1. Introduction

The current AI technology and large language model seem to bring a new challenge to educators and increase the concern about using AI will cause plagiarism and academic dishonesty (Iqbal et al., 2023; Susnjak, 2022; Tatzel & Mael, 2023; Ventayen, 2023b). Since OpenAI released a free version of ChatGPT to the public in November 2022, within a short period of time, over a million users have used the ChatGPT online application (Hu, 2023; OpenAI, 2022b). Over 334 thousand tweets on ChatGPT were generated on Twitter within two and a half months after its launch (Leiter et al., 2023). This shows that ChatGPT has generated significant interest in the AI field. Although the fame of ChatGPT has drawn substantial attention rapidly, it also brings up concerns in various aspects, particularly in higher educational environments.

1.1. The Power of ChatGPT

Scholars have been testing the power of ChatGPT with overwhelming results. For example, ChatGPT not only performed with a B grade in an MBA operation management exam but also was able to provide excellent explanations for its answers (Terwiesch, 2023). ChatGPT could perform well in law exams too. It can pass the four separate law final exams with a grade of C+, which includes approximately a hundred mixed multiple-choice and essay questions (Choi et al., 2023). Moreover, without any radiology-specific pre-training, ChatGPT was able to achieve a 69% mark in assessments, which almost passed the radiology examination (Bhayana et al., 2023). Similarly, in the United States Medical Licensing Examination (USMLE), ChatGPT also was at and nearly passed in different areas without any specialised training beforehand (Kung et al., 2022). The results indicate that if ChatGPT was trained with the relevant contents, it could pass the medical subjects as well. These studies not merely have demonstrated the power of ChatGPT, but they have also generated concerns in the education field.

With the power of ChatGPT, researchers started to focus on the impact of ChatGPT on plagiarism and academic integrity. The maturity of ChatGPT generating text can lead a student to a shortcut to success effortlessly (Khalil & Er, 2023). The content generated by ChatGPT can also easily bypass the plagiarism checking software, which creates room for students to use such technology for cheating, threatening academic honesty and endangering academic integrity, especially in the higher education sector (Susnjak, 2022; Ventayen, 2023b). Given ChatGPT's capabilities, the educators' concerns are valid. Particularly with a report of a 153% increase in plagiarism incidents in 2019 at the University of Auckland (Henry, 2022). To safeguard academic integrity from the new shock caused by ChatGPT, numerous colleges and universities have initiated responsive measures in the control of plagiarism.

1.2. Tertiary Education and Academic Responses

In 2023, numerous tertiary education institutions, such as the University of Cambridge, the University of Oxford, Sciences Po, Sophia University, and the University of Hong Kong banned

the use of ChatGPT with the reason of avoiding plagiarism. Australian jurisdictions have restricted school internet access to ChatGPT (A. Davis, 2023). Furthermore, academic journals also have concerns about Generative AI (GenAI) technology such as ChatGPT, denying the role of ChatGPT as an author for publications (Flanagin et al., 2023). Arguably, ChatGPT is not an actual author due to the fact that 63% of ChatGPT-generated abstracts were fake (Thorp, 2023). Journals also banned ChatGPT as an author for publications with the concern of authenticity of information, stating that researchers must be meticulous with attention to details and rigorous inspection of information sources to uphold the scientific conduct and maintain trust (International Committee of Medical Journal Editors, 2023; International Conference on Machine Learning, 2023; Nature, 2023; Thorp, 2023). While these responses are putting the ChatGPT in a more controllable position, not all higher education institutions and scholars share the same view.

On the contrary, Polonsky and Rotman (2023) argued that ChatGPT has the capability to meet the requirement of co-authorship since it can analyse data, draft articles, and ensure accuracy with its large language model and machine learning ability. Thus, ChatGPT can be a co-author to contribute and enhance the research process, content precision, and generate innovation. Some universities such as Singapore University of Technology and Design (2023), The Education University of Hong Kong (2023), and The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology (2023) accepted students using ChatGPT as an assisting tool in their preparation of assignments as a new phenomenon. These universities assert that GenAI tools like ChatGPT can stimulate innovative thinking, accelerate the critical thinking process, aid in complex academic tasks, and at the same time promote self-regulated learning that enables students to prepare for the evolution to the digital future. Flinders University (2023), Korea University (2023) and University of Queensland (2023) also support students to use ChatGPT with the aim of utilising the AI power in education practice and evaluation. To ensure students with the necessary knowledge of ethically using AI technology, and protecting them from academic misconduct, they provide guidelines and workshops to assist students and academic staff in applying ChatGPT for assignments and assessments (see Table 1).

Table 1. Comparison of ChatGPT Stances at Different Universities

Allow	Allow (Providing Guidelines)	Ban
Singapore University of Technology and Design	University of Queensland	University of Cambridge
The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology	Korea University	University of Oxford
The Education University of Hong Kong	University of California	Sciences Po
	Flinders University	Sophia University
		The University of Hong Kong

Different universities and scholars treat ChatGPT with different approaches. Whether using ChatGPT in the academic world is concerned with plagiarism or harnessing innovation for the digital future, there is a lack of consensus in academia. Despite that, one thing that researchers can align with is that the ChatGPT or generative AI is a disruptive technology which brings a huge impact on the existing learning practices in higher education and the academic world (Chow et al., 2023; Dwivedi et al., 2023; Flanagan et al., 2023; Frith, 2023; Haque et al., 2022).

1.3. Problem Statement

Despite the increasing number of debates about using ChatGPT in the education field, there is a limited understanding of the factors that influence tertiary students to use it in their studies. Meanwhile, some research has analysed the ChatGPT on social media such as Twitter, examining its impacts on education (Haque et al., 2022; Leiter et al., 2023; Mogavi et al., 2023), which did not delve deeply into student perspectives on the usage of ChatGPT. Sullivan et al. (2023) carried out a content analysis from the mainstream English media from Australia, New Zealand, the United States, and the United Kingdom, highlighted the media solely focused on the effect of plagiarism and that the student's perspectives on using ChatGPT are neglected. These observations pinpoint a research gap in understanding the student's opinions. Therefore, the aim of this research is to identify and analyse the factors that influence tertiary students in the use of ChatGPT to provide insights for educators and institutions to enhance students' learning experiences with AI technology, as well as contributing to the enhancement of education.

1.4. Research Motivation

The motivation behind my research is that we are living in the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, where AI is one of the important parts of this revolution (Butler-Adam, 2018). It is my privilege to be able to contribute insights to different stakeholders including students, education providers and policymakers in the education industry and possibly help to shape future learning.

1.5. Research Objectives

- To identify the factors that influence the tertiary students' use of ChatGPT in their studies.
- To examine the influence of ChatGPT on motivating students to complete their academic tasks.
- To investigate the potential plagiarism that affects students' willingness to adopt ChatGPT for their academic works.

2. Literature Review

This literature review covered the Use and Gratification Theory (U&G) and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) in the context of AI. The aims of this literature review were: (a) to investigate the existing knowledge related to the using AI, chatbot and generative AI like ChatGPT as a tool for education; (b) to identify the research gap(s) to understand students' perspectives; (c) to develop hypotheses that bridged the identified gap(s).

2.1. Theoretical Frameworks

U&G Theory is a psychological communication model that is to comprehend the underlying reasons for individuals' utilisation of specific media, their motivations for using it, and the gratifications they derive from such usage (Kasirye, 2021; Katz et al., 1973). For this research, the aspects of cognitive and tension release needs from U&G theory will be used to formulate two hypotheses. TAM is widely recognised in research and used to explain how users perceive and adopt new technologies, focusing on the cognitive process with the aim of satisfying the user and maximising the usefulness of the technology. TAM suggests three key elements to understand user interaction with technology, which include perceived usefulness; perceived ease of use; and intention to use (Legris et al., 2003; Muchran & Ahmar, 2019).

2.2. Cognitive Need

The incorporation of AI in educational settings has enriched student learning experiences, and AI has the capability to facilitate the customisation and individualisation of learning resources, catering to each student's learning style and ability (Bhutoria, 2022; Russell & Norvig, 2010). The use of chatbots offers convenient and simple access to information and resources for students, which has a positive impact on students' academic performances and develops their decision-making skills (Okonkwo & Ade-Ibijola, 2021). Students who use chatbots for learning display enjoyment and improvement in language skills (Kohnke, 2023). It benefits tertiary students in self-regulated learning and assists individuals in implementing metacognition to enhance their learning

outcomes (Sáiz-Manzanares et al., 2023). Furthermore, chatbots can motivate and foster curiosity and ask challenging questions, thereby stimulating intrinsic motivation (Winkler & Söllner, 2018).

Moreover, ChatGPT can translate complex contents such as programming codes and radiology reports into easily understanding language that can enhance communication between healthcare professionals, patients, and users (Cox et al., 2023; Lyu et al., 2023; Rahman & Watanobe, 2023), motivating and engaging students learning (Muñoz et al., 2023). Especially, using ChatGPT for teaching increases English learners' intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, (Ali et al., 2023; Kohnke, 2023). In other words, as ChatGPT is a chatbot, it can generate human-like content and can be easily understood based on the user's commands or questions. Therefore, it can be inferred that ChatGPT can motivate tertiary students and foster their confidence in self-regulated learning, (Sáiz-Manzanares et al., 2023). Cognitive needs in U&G theory relate to the need for knowledge and understanding, which shows that people choose certain media to get information (Kasirye, 2021). If students are motivated to learn, they tend to get more information out of what they're studying or using (Ruggiero, 2000).

2.3. Tension Release Need

Tertiary students often experience a high level of anxiety. Over half of the university students in Hong Kong have some degree of depressive and anxiety symptoms (Lun et al., 2018). Likewise, nearly 40% of New Zealand tertiary students reported having sleep disorders due to stress and anxiety (Samaranayake et al., 2014). Over 86% of students in South America also have generalised anxiety that could cause poor academic performance (Dias Lopes et al., 2020). Subsequently, hard-to-comprehend lectures, challenges in adapting to university life, and solving problems independently are the causes of generating students' anxieties, which could impact their study performance (Muñoz et al., 2023).

Ayedoun et al. (2015) suggested a computer-based conversational agent could reduce the student's anxiety and increase their willingness to communicate. It is because when students talk to computer-based conversational agents, they perceive a mistake-friendly environment which provides them a chance to practice without embarrassment. On the other hand, chatbots can be

used for self-diagnosis of health and mental health intervention for users who are unwilling to seek advice because of fear of judgment (Abd-Alrazaq et al., 2019; Shahsavar & Choudhury, 2023). Similarly, tertiary students may have difficulties accessing to institution's learning resources or be reluctant to reach out for learning assistance due to shyness. This non-judgmental environment caters to the student's cognitive needs for knowledge and understanding. In addition, the chatbot also provides emotional support to students as a counselling tool (Okonkwo & Ade-Ibijola, 2021). Despite ChatGPT not having emotion and empathy and not providing emotional support that is equivalent to human teachers due to its emotionless AI nature (Chan & Hu, 2023; Chan & Lee, 2023), it can perform repetitive tasks, allowing students to ask the same question repeatedly for clarification without location and time limitations (Atlas, 2023; Ayedoun et al., 2015). Furthermore, as ChatGPT can translate complex content into simpler terms (Cox et al., 2023; Lyu et al., 2023; Rahman & Watanobe, 2023), this could also help students to reduce their anxiety levels. Since ChatGPT is now accessible for tertiary students, it serves as an AI assistant that can enhance student productivity (Fauzi et al., 2023). With such convenience and efficiency, ChatGPT can reduce student's workload and stress which contribute to their tension release needs, helping them to build up confidence in their studies.

2.4. The Perceived Ease of Use

The perceived ease of use (PEU) in TAM represents the users' perspective on how easy or difficult technology is to use and how readily the users accept such technology (F. D. Davis, 1989). If the technology can be easily used without complex learning of how to use it, the technology is more likely to be perceived as useful and more likely to continue using it (Muchran & Ahmar, 2019). When users select to use an application, the comfort level, simplicity, and pleasure of using it are considered to be the factors that influence the PEU (Wulandari & Widiatoro, 2017). A well-designed and user-friendly chatbot has a direct impact on the students utilising it as a learning tool (Winkler & Söllner, 2018). As a chatbot offers simplicity, convenience, and ease of operation, it increases user satisfaction (D. Huang & Chueh, 2021). Chatbots shift the focus from usability design to enhancing user interaction, which primarily relies on the user's input (Følstad & Brandtzæg, 2017). Instead of expecting users to adapt and undergo a learning process on how to

operate the application, the chatbot provides an intuitive interface, easing the users' learning curve by allowing them to type their queries into the chat field to engage with the AI technology, ensuring the users can utilise the tool without needing a deep understanding of its underlying mechanics (Fadhil, 2018; Qasse et al., 2021). In general, when interacting with educational chatbots, students felt it was easy to communicate and did not get confused (Hew et al., 2021). Whereas Damerji and Haque (2020) also found that PEU positively influences students in AI technology adoption.

In addition, the ability of a chatbot to memorise user interactions for future reference can be convenient for users. Its capability to handle ambiguity and erroneous inputs from users and be able to provide correct responses, or ask for clarification, is the key to the component to facilitate the interaction between human users and the AI system (Khanna et al., 2015). Considering the students who are not familiar with the subject, writing errors often include typographical errors, misspellings, and wrong syntax, the role of a chatbot becomes important to recognise these errors, understand the user's intended context, and provide corrective suggestions (Kuligowska, 2015; Okuda & Shoda, 2018). These chatbot functionalities contribute to the PEU and have a direct impact on the learner's experience. In light of this, ChatGPT is a chatbot with a simple text-based interface, possessing the ability to comprehend the learners' intended meaning, making it a potential tool for students to continuously use for learning.

2.5. Gender Difference in Adopting ChatGPT

Gender is one of the factors that may impact the inclination to adopt AI technology. There is a disparity between males and females on how they feel their abilities in proficient in technology (Sobieraj & Krämer, 2020). Raman et al. (2023) found distinct preferences between genders when choosing ChatGPT as a learning tool. Female students thought the PEU was the first priority, whereas male students rated the PEU as the second important factor when adopting ChatGPT in their studies. In line with this, Yilmaz et al. (2023) also discovered there is a substantial difference in terms of perceived ease of use in ChatGPT between male and female students. Male students generally demonstrated greater confidence in mastering ChatGPT and found it easier to use in comparison with female students.

2.6. The Perceived Usefulness

The user's perceived usefulness (PU) is another critical component in the adoption of technology in TAM. PU is a variable that measures the users' belief and adopting a particular technology to enhance productivity (F. D. Davis, 1989). It can affect the users' consideration in adopting the technology (Muchran & Ahmar, 2019).

The rapid development of Internet technology has substantially increased the volume of academic papers. Growing from one million publications in the 1980s to more than seven million annually in the new millennium (Herrmannova & Knoth, 2016). Such information overload can negatively impact learners, reducing learning efficiency and productivity, decreasing learner comprehension, and affecting their decision-making (Feroz et al., 2022; Jonaityte, 2016). Even though technology is contributing to this overflow of information, which negatively impacts tertiary students' academic performance and learning efficiency (Al-Kumaim et al., 2021; Suhaimi & Hussin, 2017), it also offers solutions to overcome this situation. AI tools can process large amounts of data to provide personalised learning to enhance study efficiency (Gao et al., 2021; Luan et al., 2020). With the aid of ChatGPT, it can help students to process data in the information overload situation, and manage their learning efficiently, resulting in a high level of perceived usefulness among students, as it significantly simplifies their academic tasks and information processing.

As ChatGPT-3 was trained with 175 billion parameters which is 10 times more than the previous version, it possesses the ability to answer queries on a wide range of academic topics (Brown et al., 2020; Lund & Wang, 2023). With its machine learning (ML) and generating content based on the user's queries, ChatGPT is not only being suggested to be the tool to personalise learning for individual learners (Farrokhnia et al., 2023; Kasneci et al., 2023), it is recognised by scholars as a versatile tool for self-learning (Atlas, 2023; Biswas, 2023; Firat, 2023; Lin, 2023). Furthermore, learning with ChatGPT can foster creativity through brainstorming sessions, due to its capacity to create diversified content, encouraging users to explore new ideas (Halaweh, 2023; Sok & Heng, 2023). Drawing from this insight, ChatGPT plays an important role as a mentor, an analysis assistant, and a support writing tool to researchers and students (Berg, 2023), helping

students triage their assignment issues and therefore improve efficiency. Chan and Hu (2023) pinpointed that tertiary students in Hong Kong would continue using the GenAI tools for their learning, despite recognising the tools' limitations.

However, this perceived usefulness might have unintended consequences. User trust has a positive influence on adopting ChatGPT, hence users may heavily rely on ChatGPT for health-related advice. A mechanism should be in place in chatbots to preclude user over-reliance (Choudhury & Shamszare, 2023; Kretzschmar et al., 2019). With this in mind, students may become reliant on ChatGPT, using it as an aid for most of their academic tasks (Fuchs, 2023; Kasneci et al., 2023). The educators also expressed their concern that such GenAI technology could lead to student's over-reliance (Chan & Lee, 2023).

2.7. Intention to Use

The Intention to Use (ITU) is another important element in TAM. It is a variable that is directly influenced by the PU and PEU, helping to gauge the user's behavioural intention to use a particular application in the future (F. D. Davis, 1989). Despite teachers' hesitation in using ChatGPT in the classroom (Iqbal et al., 2023), Liu and Ma (2023) argued learners have a greater degree of behavioural intention to use ChatGPT outside of the classroom if they feel it is useful. Students think ChatGPT is useful not only in education but also in helping their careers (Shoufan, 2023). Additionally, other scholars also revealed the user experience, expected performance of ChatGPT, hedonic motivation, and value in price and learning significantly influenced the behaviour intention of Spanish and Malaysian students (Foroughi et al., 2023; Romero Rodríguez et al., 2023). In contrast, Bonsu and Baffour-Koduah (2023) found that there is no statistical relationship between Ghanaian student's perception and intention to use ChatGPT for study. Although varying results were examined, a quasi-experimental design done by Alneyadi and Wardat (2023) indicated that students with ChatGPT aids have a positive influence on their academic achievement. Such a result implies that ChatGPT has revolutionised the research in academia, acting as a versatile tool that can enhance academic and student performance (Biswas, 2023; Kasneci et al., 2023). When students employ ChatGPT to improve efficiency for assignment completion, they are more likely to continue using the tool because of its ability to enhance their

workflow, as well as adding value to their academic performance. Nonetheless, limited research has been conducted from the student perspective on whether they intend to use ChatGPT in order to improve their academic performance.

2.8. The Perceived Risk of Plagiarism

Plagiarism involves copying another person's work, concept or even way of expression and presenting it as one own without appropriate acknowledgement, which is considered dishonesty or misconduct in academia (Park, 2006). As discussed in the introduction, many universities and educational institutions prohibited students from using ChatGPT for their assignments, diligently trying to prevent students from plagiarising content that does not stem from students' learning. In fact, with the power and capability of ChatGPT that can produce human-like writing easily, the concerns of misusing ChatGPT have been raised. The perceptions of university educators were mostly unfavourable about the use of ChatGPT due to their predominant worries were the potential cheating and plagiarism (Iqbal et al., 2023). Scholars also held the same worries that generative AI technology might wrongly encourage students to go academic shortcuts and threaten integrity (Khalil & Er, 2023; Susnjak, 2022; Tlili et al., 2023).

Despite this, plagiarism in education is not a new circumstance. However, with new technological aids, the patterns of student plagiarising have changed (Uzun & Kilis, 2020). Studies have shown over 50% of students have thought to use the content produced by ChatGPT for assignments (Ventayen, 2023a), and Tatzel and Mael (2023) specifically argued the abusive use of ChatGPT for cheating is AI plagiarism. Besides the plagiarism problem, the use of ChatGPT may result in creating an inequitable advantage for some students in comparison to their peers who did not use the AI tools for assessment (Cotton et al., 2023). The content generated by ChatGPT might miss its context, providing mistaken and containing favouritism information that can deceive readers and even blind reviewers (Dahmen et al., 2023). In contrast, Lin (2023) argued that it is unreasonable to disqualify the content that is generated from AI and is treasured by the peer reviewer. As the debate continues, it becomes imperative to have clear guidelines on AI-generated content for higher education.

Given the concerns that using AI technology may further foster a climate of plagiarism, it is important to understand plagiarism from a student's perspective, as this can turn the culture of cheating into a culture of learning (Cronan et al., 2018). However, a large amount of media coverage overly focused on plagiarism issues, yet it lacks the student perspectives (Sullivan et al., 2023). The media interpretation of ChatGPT could elevate a perceived risk of plagiarism and prevent students from using ChatGPT as a learning tool. The perceived risk can impact the ITU and bring negative association with the use of chatbots (Kasilingam, 2020), and it also has a direct relationship to a student's plagiaristic behaviours (Lau et al., 2013). Given that perceived risk is a suggested variable that could impact the ITU in the TAM model (Featherman, 2001; Winarto & Panjaitan, 2021), it could impact the students' use of ChatGPT. From the U&G Theory perspective, the increased perceived risk of plagiarism may not fulfil the tension release needs, rather, it could increase the students' stress levels.

2.9. Research Questions

Based on the literature review, three research questions were formed:

- RQ1: What are the factors for tertiary students to use ChatGPT in their learning?
- RQ2: What is the degree of reliance on ChatGPT by students in their learning?
- RQ3: How does the use of ChatGPT affect students' motivation to incorporate it into their academic works?

2.10. Hypotheses

Table 2 Hypotheses

H1	Using ChatGPT enhances the motivation of students in their studies.
H2	The use of ChatGPT relieves learning-related anxiety among students.
H3	The perceived ease of use of ChatGPT positively influences the amount students use it for study.

H4	There is a significant difference in the perceived ease of use of ChatGPT between male and female students.
H5	The perceived usefulness of ChatGPT is positively associated with the reliance of students for studies.
H6	The intention to use ChatGPT is positively correlated with the perceived enhancement in academic performance.
H7	The risk of plagiarism negatively influences the use of ChatGPT in studies.

Based on the present literature and considering ChatGPT as an academic tool for tertiary students, the following hypotheses are created (Table 2). Although the factors that affect technology adoption have been explored in the existing literature, there remains a gap in understanding how these factors influence the usage of ChatGPT from a tertiary student viewpoint, particularly in the New Zealand context. By examining the above factors, where a gap is between these variables, this study aims to bridge the gap by mixing two frameworks. To provide a clearer understanding of the research framework and the relationships between variables and the research topic, a diagram is presented (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework (Source: Author, 2023)

3. Method

This research was cross-sectional, as it takes a snapshot of a specific moment and phenomenon. This approach utilises a questionnaire to explain in what way the factors relate to the observed phenomenon (Saunders et al., 2019). Since ChatGPT represents a GenAI phenomenon, which is currently influencing tertiary students' use of GenAI tools for their studies, it is important to conduct an investigation and understand this education trend.

Primary data for this study was collected from students in Auckland City attending a diverse range of educational institutions offering programs from New Zealand Diplomas (NZQA level 5) to master's degrees (NZQA level 9). To enhance the research's reliability, the questionnaire was also distributed to students in other New Zealand cities and invited them to take part in the research. This could provide a comprehensive perspective on the use of ChatGPT in the New Zealand context. This research primarily focused on collecting categorical data, which included demographical questions (e.g., genders and level of study) and hypothesis-driven questions using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree" (Allen & Seaman, 2007; Saunders et al., 2019). In 2022, there are 241,815 full-time equivalent tertiary students in New Zealand (Ministry of Education, 2023). To ensure the findings of this research are statistically significant, 385 of the sample size was expected to be collected.

3.1. Questionnaire Mapping

Table 3. Questionnaire Mapping

Hypothesis	Item	Questionnaire
H4	DEM1	What is your gender?
Generic Items	GEN1	I have experience in using ChatGPT for my studies
	GEN1a	How frequently do you use ChatGPT for your assignments or academic tasks?
	GEN1b	What is/are the reason(s) that prevent you from using ChatGPT for your studies? (Please select ALL that apply)
H1	USE1	ChatGPT is as knowledgeable as a human lecturer.
	USE2	ChatGPT adapts to my learning speed.
	USE3	ChatGPT provides informative knowledge for my study.
	MOT1	Using ChatGPT encourages me to ask more study-related questions.
	MOT2	Incorporating ChatGPT into my study increases my motivation to learn.
	MOT3	I feel more confident when I use ChatGPT to learn in my studies.
H2	USE4	ChatGPT provides a mistake-friendly environment for my studies.

	USE5	ChatGPT guides my studies when I'm feeling confused.
	USE6	ChatGPT simplifies difficult subjects, making them easier for me to understand.
	STR1	ChatGPT is available anytime I need assistance in my studies.
	STR2	Incorporating ChatGPT into my study relieves my study stress.
	STR3	I feel less stress in my study after using ChatGPT as a learning tool.
H3	PEU1	ChatGPT is easy to use in my learning.
	PEU2	I don't need to spend additional time learning how to use ChatGPT.
	PEU3	The ChatGPT chatting interface feels like I'm conversing with a real person.
	PEU4	ChatGPT understands my typo errors and grasp what I actually mean.
	PEU5	ChatGPT provides corrective suggestions for my study.
H5	PU1	ChatGPT is useful for my studies
	PU2	ChatGPT helps me to brainstorm study-related question I have.
	PU3	ChatGPT assists me in analysing study content.
	PU4	ChatGPT generates content that I can use for reference.
	REL1	I often ask ChatGPT for study-related questions before consulting tutors or peers.
	REL2	I become reliant on ChatGPT for my studies.
H6	PERF1	ChatGPT assists me to complete my assignment effortlessly.
	PERF2	ChatGPT provides insight to my assignment content.
	PERF3	ChatGPT improves my academic grades.
	PERF4	ChatGPT saves my study time.
	ITU1	I will continue to use ChatGPT for studies
	ITU2	I see ChatGPT as an essential tool for my future studies.
H7	PLA1	Using ChatGPT for studies involves plagiarism risk.
	PLA2	My school thinks using ChatGPT can lead to plagiarism.
	USEP1	I hesitate to use ChatGPT as I'm concerned about committing unintentional AI plagiarism.
	USEP2	The concerns of academic misconduct have psychologically limited me from using ChatGPT for studies.
	USEP3	I avoid directly using ChatGPT's responses in my academic work to prevent AI plagiarism.
Generic Items	GEN2	I believe educational institutions should adopt ChatGPT to support students' learning.
	GEN3	Are you an international student or a Local Student?
	GEN4	What level of education are you currently taking?

The purpose of the questionnaire mapping was to provide a structured overview of the questions, categorising by generic items and hypothesis-driven items (see Table 3). The first page of the questionnaire sought for consent of respondents to participate in this study. The initial question (DEM1) addressed the hypotheses Ho4 and H4. Thereafter, a generic question (GEN1) served as a screening question to determine whether the participants continued the questionnaire. Respondents who had experience in using ChatGPT were directed to GEN1a and proceeded to complete the entire survey. Those without experience would answer GEN1b and complete the rest of the generic items only. Applying the screening question at the beginning could ensure the respondents with relevant experience partake in the survey to test the hypothesis-driven items. Moreover, it provided insights into the reasons why some participants might not use ChatGPT for the study (Mancosu et al., 2019).

The generic items included aspects like frequency of use, groups of students and their study levels. In contrast, the hypothesis items delved into cognitive needs, tension release needs, PEU, PU, ITU, and plagiarism risk. Moreover, it is important to note that the term “use of ChatGPT” in Hypothesis 1 (H1) and Hypothesis 2 (H2) is different from the term stated in Hypothesis 7 (H7). In H1 and H2, the obtained scores had a positive value. In contrast, the received scores for H7 had negative values. To avoid confusion, it is necessary to distinguish constructs clearly. The items related to the “use of ChatGPT” were named “USE”, while the items of using ChatGPT in a plagiarism context were labelled as “USEP”.

3.2. Testing Hypotheses

During the hypothesis testing, a comparison of the calculated correlation coefficient (r) and its significant level (α), is set at 0.05. When the r with a p-value that is less than 0.05, the H_0 is rejected (Artusi et al., 2002). Such statistical tool was applied to test H_{01} to H_{03} and H_{05} to H_{07} . However, for H_{04} , due to its nominal data type and its characteristic of investigating the gender differences in using ChatGPT, a chi-square test (χ^2) was used as a different statistical tool. Similarly, when the p-value was obtained from χ^2 is less than 0.05, the H_0 is rejected (Rana & Singhal, 2015). To achieve and prove the statistical significance, a free desktop version of Jamovi 2.3.28 was employed for analysing the collected data.

While Pearson’s correlation test and chi-square test both require only two variables, the constructs encompassing multiple items may not be directly suitable for hypothesis tests. In order to address this issue, a composite scoring approach was applied for each construct. Given that the internal consistency of multiple items generated results above 0.7 in the pre-test survey, the average value (mean score) of various items in the same category was calculated.

3.3. Results of Reliability and Validity Tests

Table 4. Reliability Test

<i>Items</i>	<i>Cronbach Alpha if Item Dropped</i>	<i>Cronbach Alpha</i>
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<i>Use of ChatGPT (USE)</i>	USE1	0.814	0.844
	USE2	0.805	
	USE3	0.816	
	USE4	0.836	
	USE5	0.812	
	USE6	0.826	
<i>Motivation (MOT)</i>	MOT1	0.790	0.795
	MOT2	0.629	
	MOT3	0.725	
<i>Stress Release (STR)</i>	STR1	0.881	0.783
	STR2	0.570	
	STR3	0.611	
<i>Perceived Ease of Use (PEU)</i>	PEU1	0.690	0.749
	PEU2	0.714	
	PEU3	0.757	
	PEU4	0.673	
	PEU5	0.680	
<i>Perceived Usefulness (PU)</i>	PU1	0.717	0.799
	PU2	0.736	
	PU3	0.695	
	PU4	0.843	
<i>Reliant (REL)</i>	REL1	0.630	0.755
	REL2	0.584	
<i>Academic Performance (PERF)</i>	PERF1	0.798	0.851
	PERF2	0.830	
	PERF3	0.794	
	PERF4	0.822	
<i>Intention to Use (ITU)</i>	ITU1	0.709	0.845
	ITU2	0.756	
<i>Plagiarism Risk (PLA)</i>	PLA1	0.539	0.602
	PLA2	0.358	
<i>Use of ChatGPT in Plagiarism (USEP)</i>	USEP1	0.634	0.758
	USEP2	0.643	
	USEP3	0.745	

Figure 2. Eigenvalue Scree Plot: Number of Retained Components

In the actual reliability analysis, Cronbach alpha coefficients were calculated for each scale to measure the internal consistency. Most scales demonstrated strong reliability Cronbach Alpha values (0.749 to 0.851), exceeded the commonly accepted level of 0.7 (Bujang et al., 2018; Taber, 2018) (see Table 4). However, only the plagiarism risk (PLA) demonstrated weak reliability (0.602). This result reflected that students’ responses to the perceived plagiarism risk (PLA1) did not align with their belief that their school considers ChatGPT as a potential plagiarism tool (PLA2). Moreover, based on the Principal Component Analysis (PCA), the result suggested that this construct can be streamlined by reducing it to six components (see Figure 2).

3.4. Model Fit

Table 5. Model Fit Indices for Research Construct

Chi-Square		RMSEA 90% CI
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χ^2	df	p	SRMR	RMSEA	Lower	Upper
1059	482	< 0.001	0.0566	0.0723	0.0722	0.0863

To assess how well did constructs fit into the research model, SRMR (Standardised Root Mean Square Residual) and RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation) were utilised. The chi-square fit index was also used to examine the hypothesised model against the data. A p-value was < 0.05 indicates a good model fit (Alavi et al., 2020; Shi et al., 2018). The SRMR result was 0.0566 (< 0.08), the RMSEA was 0.0723 (< 0.08) and the chi-square p-value was < 0.001, which was less than the 0.05 standard. Based on the SRMR and RMSEA results the model was considered a good fit (see Table 5).

4. Results

Table 6. Demographical Data

		<i>Have ChatGPT Experience (n)</i>			
	Categories	No	Yes	Total	Percentages (%)
Gender	Female	57	120	177	52
	Male	39	102	141	41.5
	Preferred not to answer	15	7	22	6.5
Type of Students	International Students	61	112	173	50.9
	Local Students	50	117	167	49.1
Academic Level	Level 7 - Bachelor's degree	35	120	155	45.6
	Level 9 - Master's degree	47	70	117	34.4
	Level 4 / below - NZ Certificate	12	21	33	9.7
	Level 8 – Postgraduate	8	9	17	5
	Level 5-6 - NZ Diploma	6	5	11	3.2
	Level 10 - Doctoral Degree	3	4	7	2.1

The survey was conducted in September 2023, and within two weeks, it successfully collected three hundred forty responses ($n = 340$) in Auckland, New Zealand, reached 88.3% of the target sample size. As a result, it may influence the generalisability of the study's findings to a wider student population. 52% of respondents are female students ($n = 177$), 41.5% of respondents are males ($n = 141$) and 6.5% of respondents preferred not to answer their gender. The result had 50.9% of respondents were international students ($n = 173$) and 49.1% were local students ($n = 167$). This study included respondents from various study levels in New Zealand. It encompassed from NZQF Level 10 doctoral degree candidates ($n = 7$) to Level 4 or below students ($n = 33$). Among different education levels, Level 7 students ($n = 155$) and Level 9 students ($n = 117$) took 80% of the total respondents. These diversified samples ensured the results reflected a broad spectrum of students' perspectives across NZ tertiary education (see Table 6).

Figure 3. Level of Study and using ChatGPT

In terms of having experience using ChatGPT as a learning tool, an analysis of respondents' feedback revealed diversified results across different study levels. Nearly 60% of the Level 10 (n = 4) and 60% of Level 9 respondents (n = 70) claimed they use ChatGPT for studies. For Level 4 or below, it was slightly higher at around 64% (n = 21). Level 8 was about 53%, whereas Levels 5 – 6 was slightly lower at around 45%. Notably, 77% of Level 7 students reported using ChatGPT for their studies (n = 120), representing one-third of the total sample size, thus significantly influencing the overall results (see Figure 3).

Figure 4. Gender and Use of ChatGPT

When investigating from a gender perspective, similar patterns emerged in both male and female adoption of ChatGPT as a learning tool. Almost 70% of female students ($n = 120$) and slightly over 70% of male students ($n = 102$) expressed they have utilised ChatGPT for their study tasks. Among those who preferred not to disclose their gender, just over 30% of them said they used ChatGPT. This observation suggested that while male and female students' patterns of adoption are somewhat aligned, there might be other underlying factors that influence the individuals not to opt in based on their gender (see Figure 4).

4.1. Students' Experience with ChatGPT vs. Support for Its Educational Adoption

Table 7. Chi-square test (Students Experience in ChatGPT vs Support Adopting in Education)

	<i>Value</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
χ^2	52.0	4	<0.001
<i>n</i>	340		

To better understand students' beliefs about the formal adoption of ChatGPT by educational institutions, a chi-square test was conducted. As Table 7 shown, the chi-square value (χ^2) is 52.0 with 4 degrees of freedom ($df = 4$), and the p-value is < 0.001 . This result indicated a significant difference in the two groups of students. Students who had experience using ChatGPT for their studies tended to support the idea that educational institutions should adopt ChatGPT to help student learning. In contrast, students who lacked ChatGPT experience were more likely to hold an opposing opinion.

4.2. Reasons for Not Using ChatGPT for Studies

Figure 5. Having Experience Using ChatGPT for Studies

I have experience in using ChatGPT for my studies

340 responses

Figure 6. Reasons for Not Adopting ChatGPT for Studies

Less than one-third of students (32.6%) claimed they did not incorporate ChatGPT for their learning (see Figure 5), and their top reasons for not adopting ChatGPT were defined as unfamiliar with the programme (29%), worrying AI plagiarism (27%), and lectures or institutions disallowance to use (20%), as considered plagiarism and restrictions from educational institutions are the deterrent effects for students (see

Figure 6). Additionally, the qualitative data gathered from the open-ended question reflected the respondents provided varied reasons for their reluctance to use ChatGPT. One respondent expressed, "It's new and I don't trust it enough. Also, I want to go through the research process on my own to hone my skills", which indicated concerns about trusting in emergent technologies like ChatGPT. Another respondent considered the issue from an ethical point of view, and claimed, "I am opposed to it on ethical grounds". Another student believed the conventional search method was sufficient for the academic tasks, noted, "I haven't come across a situation where I really needed to use ChatGPT, [since] I can just search things up on Google instead if I'm unsure". Particularly among research students, they seemed to have a concern about data privacy as one of the respondents mentioned "I am a research student, I do not want to feed any part of my work into its (ChatGPT) training data".

4.3. Students Who Have Experience Using ChatGPT for Studies

Figure 7. Frequency of Using ChatGPT

Over two-thirds of the respondents (67.4%, $n = 229$) had experienced the use of ChatGPT in their studies (see Figure 5). Based on the collected data regarding the frequency of ChatGPT

use among students, nearly half of the respondents claimed they rarely or occasionally use ChatGPT (47%), which indicated that they are using ChatGPT for learning infrequently. 28% of students claimed that they are moderate users, and 25% of students shared that they are frequent users (see Figure 7). This result indicated students might somewhat rely on ChatGPT as a learning tool for their academic tasks.

4.3.1. Factors of Using ChatGPT

Table 8. Use of ChatGPT

<i>Item</i>	<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
<i>USE1</i>	ChatGPT is as knowledgeable as a human lecturer.	2.97	1.26
<i>USE2</i>	ChatGPT adapts to my learning speed.	3.33	1.02
<i>USE3</i>	ChatGPT provides informative knowledge for my study.	3.59	1.00
<i>USE4</i>	ChatGPT provides a mistake-friendly environment for my studies.	2.89	1.25
<i>USE5</i>	ChatGPT guides my studies when I'm feeling confused.	3.80	1.04
<i>USE6</i>	ChatGPT simplifies difficult subjects, making them easier for me to understand.	3.84	1.06
<i>MOT1</i>	Using ChatGPT encourages me to ask more study-related questions	3.34	1.15
<i>MOT2</i>	Incorporating ChatGPT into my study increases my motivation to learn.	3.01	1.25
<i>MOT3</i>	I feel more confident when I use ChatGPT to learn in my studies	3.21	1.15
<i>STR1</i>	ChatGPT is available anytime I need assistance in my studies.	3.93	1.13
<i>STR2</i>	Incorporating ChatGPT into my study relieves my study stress.	3.39	1.19
<i>STR3</i>	I feel less stress in my study after using ChatGPT as a learning tool.	3.33	1.17
<i>PEU1</i>	ChatGPT is easy to use in my learning.	3.73	1.11
<i>PEU2</i>	I don't need to spend additional time learning how to use ChatGPT.	3.85	1.18
<i>PEU3</i>	The ChatGPT chatting interface feels like I'm conversing with a real person.	2.83	1.15
<i>PEU4</i>	ChatGPT understands my typo errors and grasp what I actually mean.	3.53	1.05
<i>PEU5</i>	ChatGPT provides corrective suggestions for my study.	3.20	1.13
<i>PUI1</i>	ChatGPT is useful for my studies	3.68	1.14
<i>PUI2</i>	ChatGPT helps me to brainstorm study-related question I have.	3.64	1.16
<i>PUI3</i>	ChatGPT assists me in analysing study content.	3.45	1.14
<i>PUI4</i>	ChatGPT generates content that I can use for reference.	2.71	1.34

<i>REL1</i>	I often ask ChatGPT for study-related questions before consulting tutors or peers.	3.05	1.36
<i>REL2</i>	I become reliant on ChatGPT for my studies.	2.56	1.22
<i>PERF1</i>	ChatGPT assists me to complete my assignment effortlessly.	2.75	1.22
<i>PERF2</i>	ChatGPT provides insight to my assignment content.	3.20	1.13
<i>PERF3</i>	ChatGPT improves my academic grades.	2.76	1.19
<i>PERF4</i>	ChatGPT saves my study time.	3.34	1.13
<i>ITU1</i>	I will continue to use ChatGPT for studies	3.55	1.22
<i>ITU2</i>	I see ChatGPT as an essential tool for my future studies.	3.22	1.25
<i>PLA1</i>	Using ChatGPT for studies involves plagiarism risk.	3.93	1.17
<i>PLA2</i>	My school thinks using ChatGPT can lead to plagiarism.	4.17	0.95
<i>USEP1</i>	I hesitate to use ChatGPT as I'm concerned about committing unintentional AI plagiarism.	3.53	1.25
<i>USEP2</i>	The concerns of academic misconduct have psychologically limited me from using ChatGPT for studies.	3.41	1.21
<i>USEP3</i>	I avoid directly using ChatGPT's responses in my academic work to prevent AI plagiarism.	3.91	1.21

In assessing the student perspectives on using ChatGPT, Table 8 suggested that most students tended to agree with those aspects and see the value in using ChatGPT in their studies, which included providing informative knowledge (USE3, mean = 3.59, SD = 1.00), adapting to students' learning speed (USE2, mean = 3.33, SD = 1.02), guiding studies (USE5, mean = 3.80, SD = 1.04), and simplifying difficult subject for easier understanding (USE6, mean = 3.84, SD = 1.06). However, a symmetrical distribution was observed for the items whether ChatGPT is knowledgeable as a human lecturer (USE1, mean = 2.97), and it provides a mistake-friendly environment (USE4, mean = 2.89) (see Table 8). This balanced response suggested that students recognise the value of both human lecturers and ChatGPT.

4.3.2. Motivation

The items MOT1 (mean = 3.34) and MOT3 (mean = 3.21, SD = 1.15), indicated that students tend to agree ChatGPT encourages them to ask more study-related questions and allows them to feel more confident in their study. However, there was a balanced view on item MOT2

(mean = 3.01, SD = 1.25). This suggested that ChatGPT helped students' study with confidence, but it did not necessarily motivate them to learn.

4.3.3. Study Stress

The item "Incorporating ChatGPT into my study relieves my study stress" (STR2) had a mean of 3.39 and a standard deviation (SD) of 1.19. Similarly, the item "I feel less stress in my study after using ChatGPT as a learning tool" (STR3) had a mean of 3.33 with an SD of 1.17. It represented students being between neutral to agree that ChatGPT could be a stress relieving tool to support their studies. On the other hand, 68% of students (n = 156) agreed with the statement "ChatGPT is available anytime I need assistance in my studies" (STR1, mean = 3.93, SD = 1.13), implying that ChatGPT is an easily accessible learning resource.

4.3.4. Perceived Ease of Use

More than 62% of students agreed that ChatGPT is easy to use (PEU1, mean = 3.73, SD = 1.11) and they didn't need to spend extra time learning how to use it (PEU2, mean = 3.85, SD = 1.18). Over half of the students agreed that ChatGPT could understand typo prompts and their intended meaning (PEU4, mean = 3.53, SD = 1.05). The item "ChatGPT provides corrective suggestion for my study" (PEU5, mean = 3.20, SD = 1.13) suggested students are between neutral and agree with this statement. In contrast, they valued between neutral and disagree with using ChatGPT's interface as if they were talking to a human (PEU3, mean = 2.83, SD = 1.15).

4.3.5. Perceived Usefulness

Students inclined to agree with "ChatGPT is useful in my studies" (PU1, mean = 3.68, SD = 1.14), "ChatGPT helps me to brainstorm study-related questions I have" (PU2, mean = 3.64, SD = 1.16), as well as "ChatGPT assists me in analysing study content" (PU3, mean = 3.45, SD = 1.14). Given the usefulness of ChatGPT, nearly half of the students (mean = 2.71, SD = 1.34) did

not agree that the content generated by ChatGPT can be used for reference. This implied that generative content by ChatGPT may not necessarily meet the expectations of students.

4.3.6. Reliance

Students appeared to have a neutral view regarding the statement of “I often ask ChatGPT for study-related questions before consulting tutors or peers” (REL1, mean = 3.05, SD = 1.36). Moreover, they tended to disagree with the idea of becoming reliant on using ChatGPT (REL2, mean = 2.56, SD = 1.22). This self-rating reflected that, to some degree, students felt they maintained control, rather than relying too much on ChatGPT.

4.3.7. Perceived Academic Performance

The respondents tended to vary their opinions across the items of perceived academic performance. Approximately one in two students agreed with the statements of “ChatGPT provides insight to my assignment content” (PERF2, mean = 3.20, SD = 1.13) and ChatGPT saves my study time (PERF4, mean = 3.34, SD = 1.13). It signified that students believe the content generated by ChatGPT offers inspiration for their academic work and enhances their study efficiency. Given that, students tended to hold a conservative view on the statements “ChatGPT assists me to complete my assignment effortlessly” (PERF1, mean = 2.75, SD = 1.22) and “ChatGPT improves my academic grades” (PERF3, mean = 2.76, SD = 1.19). It suggested that while students perceive ChatGPT as helpful for obtaining insights and saving study time, they did not believe it alleviated their academic workload or improved their academic performance.

4.3.8. Intention to Use

Respondents had consistent views regarding their continued use of ChatGPT for their studies (ITU1, mean = 3.55, SD = 1.22) and considered it as an essential tool for future studies

(ITU2, mean = 3.22, n = 1.25). It proposed that ChatGPT is perceived as a vital learning companion tool, and students were willing to choose it to assist with their academic tasks.

4.3.9. Risk of Plagiarism

The statements “using ChatGPT for studies involves plagiarism risk” (PLA1) and “my school thinks using ChatGPT can lead to plagiarism” (PLA2) received the highest mean scores in this study, which were 3.93 (SD = 1.17) and 4.17 (SD = 0.95) respectively. Both items PLA1 and PLA2 indicated the majority of the responded students had a high level of awareness of the plagiarism risk and understood their educational institutions’ stance on potential plagiarism caused by ChatGPT.

4.3.10. Use of ChatGPT in Plagiarism Context

When students were asked about the use of ChatGPT in a plagiarism context, respondents tended to agree with the statement “I hesitate to use ChatGPT as I’m concerned about committing unintentional AI plagiarism” (USEP1, mean = 3.53, SD = 1.25) and “The concerns of academic misconduct have psychologically limited me from using ChatGPT for studies” (USEP2, mean = 3.41, SD = 1.21). Additionally, Table 8 exhibited more than half of the students (mean = 3.91, SD = 1.21) agreed with the statement “I avoid directly using ChatGPT’s responses in my academic work to prevent AI plagiarism” (USEP3). This denoted that students understand that generative content could not be fully used for their academic works to avoid AI plagiarism.

4.4. Hypotheses Testing

4.4.1. Test Results of Using ChatGPT as a Motivation Factor

Table 9. Correlation Matrix H1

Correlation Matrix		
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		USE	MOT
USE	Pearson's r	—	
	df	—	
	p-value	—	
MOT	Pearson's r	0.729	—
	df	227	—
	p-value	< .001	—

Hypothesis 1 (H1) postulated that using ChatGPT enhances the motivation of students in their studies. The independent variable in this hypothesis was the ‘use of ChatGPT’ (USE), which was generated by computing the mean value from items USE1 to USE6. Similarly, the dependent variable, ‘motivation’ (MOT) was generated by computing the mean from items MOT1 to MOT3. The correlation coefficient (r) was 0.729, and the significance level (p) was < 0.001 (Table 9). These results indicated a rejection of the null hypothesis 1 (Ho1) and consequently demonstrated a highly significant correlation between the use of ChatGPT and student motivation in their studies.

4.4.2. Test Results of Using ChatGPT as a Stress Relief Factor

Table 10. Correlation Matrix H2

Correlation Matrix			
		STR	USE
STR	Pearson's r	—	
	df	—	
	p-value	—	
USE	Pearson's r	0.696	—
	df	227	—
	p-value	< .001	—

Hypothesis 2 (H2) posited that the use of ChatGPT relieves learning-related stress among students. The variable ‘stress’ (STR) was computed as the mean of items (STR1 to STR3), and ‘USE’ was used as an individual variable. The r was 0.696, and the p -value was < 0.001 (see

Table 10). This signified a rejection of the null hypothesis 2 (Ho2) and therefore proved a highly significant correlation between the use of ChatGPT and the relief of learning-related anxiety.

4.4.3. Test Results of Perceived Ease of Use and The Amount of Using ChatGPT

Table 11. Correlation Matrix H3

Correlation Matrix			
		PEU	GEN1a
PEU	Pearson's r	—	
	df	—	
	p-value	—	
GEN1a	Pearson's r	0.506	—
	df	227	—
	p-value	< .001	—

Hypothesis 3 (H3) assumed that the perceived ease of use of ChatGPT positively influences the amount students use it for study. The mean of the Perceived Ease of Use (PEU) was calculated by using PEU1 to PEU5, and correlated with the item “How frequently do you use ChatGPT for your assignments or academic tasks?” (GEN1a), which represented students’ frequency of use. The r was 0.506, and the p-value was < 0.001 (see Table 11). This portrayed a rejection of the null hypothesis 3 (Ho3) and subsequently proved a highly significant correlation between the use of ChatGPT and PEU.

4.4.4. Test Results of Using ChatGPT as a Gender Factor

Table 12. Chi-Square Test H4

	<i>Value</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
χ^2	5.26	8	0.73
<i>n</i>	229		

Hypothesis 4 (H4) presumed there is a significant difference between male and female students in using ChatGPT. The gender item (DEM) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEU) were used to calculate the chi-square statistic. The chi-square value was based on Table 6 data of 102 male students, 120 female students, and 7 who preferred not to answer ($n = 229$) (χ^2) was 5.26 with 8 degrees of freedom ($df = 8$). The result of the p-value was 0.73, which was greater than the common significant level of 0.05. Therefore, it failed to reject the null hypothesis (Ho4) (See Table 12). It indicated that there is no statistically significant difference in the perceived ease of use of ChatGPT between males and females. Only 14% of the students ($n = 33$) disagreed that ChatGPT is easy to use. In other words, a majority of students considered ChatGPT as user-friendly across different genders in the New Zealand context.

4.4.5. Test Results of The Perceived Usefulness Relating to Reliance

Table 13. Correlation Matrix H5

Correlation Matrix			
		PU	REL
PU	Pearson's r	—	
	df	—	
	p-value	—	
REL	Pearson's r	0.657	—
	df	227	—
	p-value	< .001	—

Hypothesis 5 (H5) postulated that there is a positive association between the perceived usefulness of ChatGPT and students' reliance on it for studies. The mean of both Perceived Usefulness (PU) and reliance (REL) was calculated from PU1 to PU4 and REL1 to REL2 respectively. With an r value of 0.657 and a p-value of < 0.001 (see Table 13), the null hypothesis 5 (Ho5) was rejected. This indicated a significant correlation between the perceived usefulness of ChatGPT and students' reliance on it.

4.4.6. Test Results of Intention to Use Affecting Perceived Academic Performance

Table 14. Correlation Matrix H6

Correlation Matrix			
		PERF	ITU
PERF	Pearson's r	—	
	df	—	
	p-value	—	
ITU	Pearson's r	0.670	—
	df	227	—
	p-value	< .001	—

Hypothesis 6 (H6) posited that there is a positive connection between students' intention to use ChatGPT and their perceived academic performance. The Intention to Use (ITU) was calculated using the average of ITU1 and ITU2. Likewise, the mean from PERF1 to PERF4 was used for the perceived academic performance (PERF). Based on the result of the correlation efficiency r value was 0.670, and the p-value was < 0.001 (see Table 14), the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, it has statistically proven the positive correlation between ITU and PERF.

4.4.7. Test Results of Plagiarism Risk Impacting Using ChatGPT

Table 15. Correlation Matrix H7

Correlation Matrix			
		PLA	USEP
PLA	Pearson's r	—	
	df	—	
	p-value	—	
USEP	Pearson's r	0.498	—
	df	227	—
	p-value	< .001	—

Hypothesis 7 (H7) posited that there is a negative influence of the risk of plagiarism on the use of ChatGPT. The risk of plagiarism (PLA) was calculated by averaging the values of PLA1 and PLA2. Similarly, the mean of use of ChatGPT in a plagiarism context (USEP) was derived from USEP1 and USEP2. The result of the correlation efficiency r value was 0.498, and the p -value was < 0.001 (see Table 15). This result rejected the null hypothesis (H_07), hence it confirmed that the risk of plagiarism negatively affects the use of ChatGPT.

Based on the correlation and chi-square test results, six out of seven hypotheses were accepted, and only one was rejected. A snapshot of the inferential statistics is presented in Table 16.

Table 16. Hypotheses Test Results

<i>Hypothesis</i>	<i>Test</i>	<i>Variables</i>	<i>Statistics</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Result</i>
<i>H1</i>	Correlation	USE; MOT	$r = 0.729$	< 0.001	Accepted
<i>H2</i>	Correlation	USE; STR	$r = 0.696$	< 0.001	Accepted
<i>H3</i>	Correlation	PEU; GEN1a	$r = 0.506$	< 0.001	Accepted
<i>H4</i>	Chi-Square	PEU1; DEM	$\chi^2 = 5.26$	0.730	Rejected
<i>H5</i>	Correlation	PU; REL	$r = 0.657$	< 0.001	Accepted
<i>H6</i>	Correlation	PERF; ITU	$r = 0.670$	< 0.001	Accepted
<i>H7</i>	Correlation	PLA; USEP	$r = 0.498$	< 0.001	Accepted

5. Discussion

5.1. Factor Influencing Confidence Boosting and Anxiety Relief through the Use of ChatGPT

Drawing upon the U&G framework, the result of H1 revealed that students were not merely using it because of its functional capabilities, but also to fulfil cognitive needs, such as enhancing their motivation and boosting confidence while pursuing their academic studies (Chang et al., 2023; P.-H. Li et al., 2023). These cognitive needs contributed to the factors influencing their adoption of ChatGPT. This insight echoed the findings of the current studies that suggest ChatGPT can be a motivating tool by advancing their knowledge, saving their time, and helping them to achieve their learning objectives (Ali et al., 2023; Muñoz et al., 2023; Romero Rodríguez et al., 2023; Yakubu & Dasuki, 2018). This also resonates with Ruggiero's concept (2000) that when students are driven by motivation to learn, they tend to get more information out of what they are studying. Likewise, the result of testing H2 suggested that those students who choose to use ChatGPT may experience some degree of study-related stress, and therefore, the tension release need is another factor that supports the use of ChatGPT, as it could relieve students' anxiety in their academic work. This finding resonates with Crawford et al. (2023) and Fauzi et al. (2023), who asserted that ChatGPT can assist students in achieving their academic objectives and enhancing their general productivity in study by offering helpful information and resources, assisting in language improvement, fostering cooperation, enhancing time efficiency and effectiveness, and offering encouragement and stress relief support to students. As both cognitive and tension release needs are the factors, it aligns with the principles of the U&G framework.

5.2. Reliance on ChatGPT

In congruence with the TAM proposed by Davis (1989), this research's findings highlight the influence of PEU, PU, and the ITU in adopting ChatGPT. Based on the TAM theory, insights have been dug out to reflect the second research question, which was set to comprehend the degree of students' reliance on ChatGPT for their studies. Although only 24.4% of students reported often

or frequently using ChatGPT, the results of H3 and H5 revealed a likelihood of increased reliance on ChatGPT. This reliance may stem from their perception of PEU and PU, which matched with other studies that reveal students find ChatGPT is user-friendly and need not to learn how to use it in advance (Bonsu & Baffour-Koduah, 2023; Hew et al., 2021; Raman et al., 2023; Yilmaz et al., 2023), these results could resonate with the concept of autodidactic learning style asserted by Firat (2023).

In addition, the boost of confidence and reduction of anxiety can serve as motivational factors, students can self-regulate their studies, set their learning objectives, and receive instant advice that suits their individual needs (Chang et al., 2023; P.-H. Li et al., 2023). Furthermore, a portion of those students who did not use ChatGPT indicated their unfamiliar with the application and felt that using Google search was sufficient for their studies. This suggested that the amount of using and relying on ChatGPT might depend on the students' familiarity with their study subjects and their comfort level with the technology. This finding could be further elaborated by H4, which proved that gender is not the factor that influences the PEU, differing from what Yilmaz et al. (2023) found, but aligned with the results by Raman et al. (2023) that PEU was at the highest priority for both male and female students when choosing ChatGPT as a learning aid. In other words, the more a student feels unfamiliar with the study subject, the higher the possibility of a student increasing their usage of technology. At the same time, if the existing technology was perceived by students as meeting their current study needs, it was more likely to stay with the current existing technology and not adopt the new one. This insight offered an extra layer of the concern raised from the result of such technology might be reliant by the students (Chan & Lee, 2023; Choudhury & Shamszare, 2023; Fuchs, 2023; Kasneci et al., 2023; Kretzschmar et al., 2019).

5.3. Concerns Regarding Academic Integrity with ChatGPT

Except for findings showing the motivational factors that lead to adopting ChatGPT, this research also signified that the use of ChatGPT is also hindered by the concern of academic integrity. From the result of H7, the perceived risk (PR) negatively influences user intention to use ChatGPT for academic tasks. From a technology adoption point of view, PR is the major barrier

for students who are unfamiliar with ChatGPT, limiting their willingness or even reluctance to adopt this technology. In contrast, students who had experience with ChatGPT expressed caution when using such technology. With the highest mean for items “Using ChatGPT for studies involves plagiarism risk” (PLA1) and “My school thinks using ChatGPT can lead to plagiarism” (PLA2), it illustrated that students acknowledge the potential of plagiarism caused by ChatGPT. Given that using ChatGPT for academic tasks may oppose their educators’ expectations and stances, the students were mitigating the risk of being accused of academic misconduct by using the generative information indirectly. They continue to see the value in using it to enhance their study efficiency and academic performance, which aligned with the H6 result. Despite the concern that ChatGPT might indirectly encourage students to take a shortcut in their academic tasks and worrying it may threaten academic integrity (Iqbal et al., 2023; Khalil & Er, 2023; Susnjak, 2022; Tlili et al., 2023), the respondents provided insights into this discussion from their perspective, stating that regardless of educators’ concerns about potential cheating and dishonesty from using ChatGPT, and banning it like some universities do (Holliday, 2023; Sciences Po, 2023; Sophia University, 2023; UNESCO, 2023), students could find a way to utilise ChatGPT or other generative AI tools to assist their self-regulated, autodidactic studies. In essence, instead of running a shortcut, the students who live in a fast-paced digital learning environment seek educational support timely and convenient, aiming to get the right guidance to adapt their learning speed, and enhance their efficiency. Thus, even though they were clear that using ChatGPT might lead to the risk of plagiarism, many students were still prone to adopt it as a learning assistant.

5.4. Conclusion

The advent of ChatGPT has undeniably brought a new phenomenon to the education sector, in particular, tertiary education. This study aimed to understand the use of ChatGPT particularly from the standpoint of New Zealand’s tertiary students, and identified and discussed several factors that influence the adoption of such technology. This study also examined how the use of ChatGPT can motivate students to complete their academic works and specifically highlighted the positive relationship between perceived ease of use and the amount of using ChatGPT; the intention to use and the perceived academic performance. The potential misuse was also explored by noting the

potential plagiarism can negatively affect the use of ChatGPT for students' studies. With these findings and results, it can confirm that the research objectives have been completely met.

5.5. Implications

The research findings pinpointed the fact that adopting ChatGPT among tertiary students is a complex issue with multidimensional factors. The insights delved from this research not only contribute to the discussion of how ChatGPT impact the education industry, but also share implications for stakeholders in the educational ecosystem.

5.5.1. Implication and Recommendation for Tertiary Student

Drawing from the findings from students' perspectives, it is evident that students possess a well understanding of ChatGPT's functionalities and capabilities in supporting their learning. The educational institutions' stance and the importance of academic integrity were clearly imprinted in students' minds as well. However, when considering the relationship between students and ChatGPT, it is vital for students to understand that they are not necessarily blind trusting the technology, but rather relying on its capabilities (Deley & Dubois, 2020). Since generative AI tools could be a new trend for any purpose, before students adopt ChatGPT for their studies, they need to identify their objectives for using it, which could be supporting a brainstorming session, clarifying theory and concepts, or even boosting academic task efficiency. Having an objective and a positive intention when using ChatGPT, it would help students to set boundaries for self-regulated learning, ensuring they are using it ethically and following the guidelines to avoid abusing using it to replace academic effort.

In addition, since ChatGPT is limited to some countries only (OpenAI, 2022a), the data training for ChatGPT may be limited, it may consequently provide non-objective information. With this in mind, students must have a "fact check" mindset, inspect the generated information, and diligently cross-check the ChatGPT contents with other sources before adopting the information.

Furthermore, while critical thinking remains a cornerstone of academic success, students should leverage it and seek diverse perspectives and cross-reference information to uphold academic standards. When using ChatGPT, it is paramount to analyse, synthesise, and edit the provided content responsibly and ensure the work is aligned with the academic integrity and honesty of their educational institutions, which is more important and cannot be replaced by Artificial Intelligence (AI).

5.5.2. Implication and Recommendation for Education Providers and Policymakers

With AI acting as one of the driving forces in the fourth Industrial Revolution (Butler-Adam, 2018), ChatGPT and other generative technologies are unavoidably evolving. Many scholars have mentioned that ChatGPT is a double-edged sword. On one hand, it revolutionises the education sector with many benefits. On the other hand, it disrupts the education industry, bringing challenges to educational institutions that they need to cope with (Dahmen et al., 2023; Hisan & Amri, 2023; Shen et al., 2023). While this double-edged sword has created an educational concern about students overly relying on ChatGPT (Chan & Lee, 2023; Fuchs, 2023; Kasneci et al., 2023), at the same time it leaves educators no choice but to rely on AI technology to counterstrike the potential AI plagiarism. As Deley and Dubois (2020) highlighted, it is important to distinguish between “relying on” and “trusting in” technology. This distinction becomes relevant as educational institutions employ technology like Turnitin for detecting potential plagiarism, creating a paradoxical situation. Solely trusting the AI plagiarism detectors might not reflect the truth of why and how students use ChatGPT, or if they are intentionally cheating.

5.5.3. For Education Providers

While educators remind students to be cautious when using ChatGPT and not solely relying on it, educators should be cautious when using AI detectors and should not solely rely on it too. When a suspicious case of plagiarism is encountered, it might be irrational for educators to declare a student guilty of AI plagiarism by just purely looking at the plagiarism similarity score. Relying on negative reinforcement in response to suspected students may not be the most effective

approach. Rather, educational leaders should hold positive intent to look at suspicious cases, demonstrate empathy, and seek to understand the underlying factors that drive students to use ChatGPT and their study challenges. Nevertheless, the mission of an educator is to support students in learning. Therefore, giving students opportunities to learn from their mistakes, discuss with them, support their rehabilitation, and help them to improve would be a more constructive approach. Moreover, education providers should also offer workshops and periodical campaigns to promote using ChatGPT responsibly. This approach can also reinforce the students on how to use the ChatGPT correctly, making them cautious when utilising the tool, and ensuring they understand its benefits, drawbacks, and the importance of protecting academic integrity.

5.5.4. For Education Policymakers

Education policymakers also need to identify factors that truly influence the students' use of ChatGPT for their studies. Clear guidelines must be established about the appropriate use of such a tool and setting the right boundaries by being transparent to send clear guidelines to students. Moreover, they can also employ dynamic strategies to measure students' learning outcomes. For example, designing a curriculum with experiential learning through internships and real-world experiences, then utilising reflective learning methods such as getting students to present their learning can strengthen their absorbed knowledge. Moreover, policymakers can also consider using research journals, study diaries or learning logs, enabling educators to trace a student's thought process and how their ideas and concepts develop over time. This approach would help educators to assess not just for the final answers from the students, but for examining the learning journey of students in critical thinking and ability to synthesise their knowledge.

5.5.5. Implication and Recommendation for GenAI Companies

Inferring from the research findings, it is clear that ChatGPT is well accepted by the students for many reasons. Meanwhile, it creates an unexpected situation for educators to defend academic honesty. As CEO of the OpenAI urged for AI regulation (Clayton, 2023), it is possible for GenAI companies to make a change that can balance the technology development while

safeguarding academic integrity. For example, the GenAI companies could develop features that only provide information sources and explanations to help students learn rather than just offering answers. The companies should also collaborate with universities and schools to develop guidelines and best practices for using ChatGPT in academic settings. Another proactive step that the companies can take is to educate and emphasise the importance of academic integrity when ChatGPT identify the student's schools and reiterates their ethical guidelines on behalf of their institutions.

5.6. Limitations

5.6.1. The Rapid Development of AI Phenomenon

Since the ChatGPT has been transiting from GPT-3.5 to a more advanced version GPT-4V(ision), which can analyse images, speak, and hear (OpenAI, 2023a, 2023b), it is trending that the generative AI will continue to develop and improve. Apart from that, education policies also evolve along with the technology shifts. For example, The University of Hong Kong (2023) changed its policy and lifted the ban on the use of ChatGPT, allowing AI tools to be incorporated into university teaching from their new academic year in September 2023. While the debates around the usage of ChatGPT in the education industry have been continuously developing, it constrains this research in terms of capturing only the latest trends and perspectives on ChatGPT and may not be able to include the latest updates.

5.6.2. Methodological Constraints and Biases

Due to the limited time frame, a non-probability method with convenience sampling was chosen for this research. With primary data collected in Auckland via instant message and social networking, there is a higher chance that the data is predominantly from Auckland City. Therefore, the survey may not be able to fully capture the New Zealand tertiary students' perspective due to a chance of neglecting other regions' respondents.

Convenient sampling was used and might impact the generalisation and the results might differ from random sampling (Acharya et al., 2013; Sharma, 2017). Subsequently, this research collected 340 samples, which represents 88.3% of the targeted sample size. Therefore, the findings may not fully generalise the broader population of students' use of ChatGPT in New Zealand.

In terms of the construct's internal consistency, it is critical to note that items under plagiarism risk (PLA) portrayed lower reliability ($\alpha = 0.602$), but it is still within the acceptable scale. This may affect the researchers to interpret the results (Sürücü & Maslakçi, 2020). Furthermore, this study's result is based on students' self-reported data, respondents filled out the survey based on their experiences and perceptions and didn't explore deeply under what conditions students cannot rely on ChatGPT. Particularly in some construct data like academic performance (PERF), it was not generated from actual students' academic results. Therefore, the results may potentially contain biases (Leedy & Ormrod, 2021; Saunders et al., 2019), and may not represent an objective view in the New Zealand context.

5.7. Future Research

Considering the limitations listed above, it might be addressed by conducting future studies. A larger scale of research extends to tertiary institutions across New Zealand which can aid researchers and educators to better understand the ChatGPT phenomenon. Instead of conducting cross-sectional research, which focuses only on a snapshot of the time, researchers can consider conducting future research with longitudinal nature which can track how ChatGPT impacts students learning in a long-term setting (Saunders et al., 2019).

In terms of tracking students' performances, confidence and anxiety, future research can apply mixed methods (quantitative and qualitative research) with split tests, dividing two groups of students and examining their learning outcome, knowledge absorb level, as well as actual academic grades (Leedy & Ormrod, 2021). Moreover, a specific group of students such as different study majors, ethnicities, and institutions can also be further investigated. Teacher perspectives from varied academic fields could also be the focus of future investigation.

Developing pedagogical strategies and designing education curricula that effectively incorporate ChatGPT into teaching and learning processes could be an investigation. This could explore how educators can scaffold students' use of ChatGPT to promote deeper learning, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills, as well as how ChatGPT could facilitate personalised learning experience that tailored to individual students' needs and preferences.

Exploring the perspectives of educators regarding the integration of ChatGPT into their teaching practices could offer valuable insights. Research in this area could study how educators utilise ChatGPT as a teaching tool, their perception of its functions in supporting student learning, as well as concerns they may have regarding its impact on academic integrity. Additionally, studying educators' attitudes towards AI plagiarism-detecting software could also reveal how AI technology be the assisting tool in the AI era.

Last but not least, future research could also consider targeting how ChatGPT can serve as an academic coach to assist students who have difficulties with their studies. It can also expand to how it influences students who have special learning needs such as Dyslexia, Dyscalculia, Dyspraxia, and Attention-deficit / Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD).

6. Ethical Approval

This research was approved by the research committee at ICL Graduate Business School Auckland, New Zealand in August 2023 (Ref No: ICL-30823-166).

7. Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interest or personal relationships which could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

8. Data Availability Statement

The data supporting this study's findings are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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